

The Assessment of the State of Digital Economy in Selected EU Countries

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Acknowledgements

The publication was co-financed by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme (HORIZON-MSCA-2021-SE-01-1); Project Number: 101086381; Project title: Overcoming Digital Divide in Europe and Southeast Asia.

Abstract

Research background: The processes of digitalization have accelerated dynamically across the European Union in recent years. Digital transformation of four Central European Countries forming the Visegrad Group (the Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland and Slovakia) is particularly interesting as it reflects the efforts made by countries with similar history and socio-economic conditions to narrow the digital divide, which is of key importance for their future socio-economic development.

Purpose of the article: The purpose of the paper is to analyse and assess the digital divide between the Visegrad countries and the EU-27 countries in the years 2017-2022.

Methods: In order to achieve this aim a comparative analysis of the performance of the Visegrad countries and the remaining EU countries was carried out based on Eurostat public statistics on the DESI and its four sub-indices. Moreover, to uncover major similarities and contrasts in the digital divide among these countries the Ward method was also used.

Findings & value added: The findings of this study contribute to the literature of digital divide of the Visegrad and the EU countries. We have shown how strongly digital divide in terms of digital access, digital skills and use is evident between these countries and the other EU Members and what are the strengths and weaknesses of their digital development strategy. We have also uncovered major similarities and contrasts in the digital divide among these countries in two specific sub-periods covering the pre-pandemic (2017-2019) and pandemic years (2019-2022). Our study results suggest the existence of rather significant differences in the level of digital development among the Visegrad countries with varying achievements in four studied dimensions of digitalization. Our research therefore brings the conclusion that the Visegrad Group cannot be perceived as a coherent block of countries, as there are still digital inequalities corresponding to different levels of the digital divide, related to the access, digital skills and use of ICT. We have also noticed, that Czech Republic constantly scored better than the other three countries. We argue that both processes – narrowing and widening of the digital divide took place in the period

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analyzed, in relation to the different levels of the divide in particular countries. But even in dimensions where positive changes have occurred, there is still considerable room for improvement.

Keywords: digital divide, digitalization, Visegrad Group, V4, European Union

1. Introduction

Digitalization has been widely recognized as one of the most significant technological megatrends, triggering an integral, fundamental process of economic, socio-political and cultural transformation observed throughout the world (Nadoleanu *et al.*, 2022). Numerous studies clearly show that differences relating to issues such as the economic performance of countries, their global competitiveness, the quality of life, education, health care, as well as environmental protection largely depend on the level of acceptance, availability and use of ICT (Kovačić *et al.*, 2022, Marti & Puertas, 2023, Yin *et al.*, 2023). However, intensified digitalization has drawn greater attention also to its negative aspects, observed at the macro-, meso- and micro- levels, which are studied in the literature as the digital divide, digital gap, digital inequalities or digital inclusion (Van Dijk, 2020, Helsper, 2021, Damiani & Rodríguez-Modroño, 2024). Whatever the name, this complex problem remains the same, leaving individuals, groups and collectives disenfranchised from the benefits of digital technologies (Robinson *et al.*, 2020). Its manifestations, scale and consequences have been particularly highlighted by the Covid-19 pandemic, which has exacerbated various pre-existing problems and disparities concerning access to and skills to use digital technologies, particularly affecting individuals and groups from vulnerable backgrounds (Kuc-Czarnecka, 2020). The pandemic has clearly shown that the digital divide is currently one of the key factors that may deepen social and economic inequalities (Ali & Faroque, 2023, Buffel *et al.*, 2023).

The European Union (EU) actively develops a number of public policies, strategies and programmes to harness potential and address challenges of digital transformation (European Commission, 2022a). Success in achieving digital goals requires a significant acceleration and deepening of member states' efforts to not only advance digitalization but also reduce the digital divide within the EU and in relation to global competitors. As shown by the latest analysis of the International Digital Economy and Society Index (I-DESI) in 2020 EU member states showed great diversity of performance in digitalization: the top four countries outperformed some of the leading economies, including the United States, United Kingdom, Canada or Japan while the bottom four EU countries performed worse than Chile, Russia, China and Serbia (European Commission, 2020, Lomba *et al.*, 2022). Also annual European Commission's DESI reports highlighted that although the EU has been significantly advancing in digitalization, there are strong disparities among member states (European Commission, 2022b).

Given the importance of bridging the digital divide for achieving the EU's digital goals and homogeneous digital development of all member states there is a need for better recognition of digital divide in European countries having different socio-economic backgrounds. Although several studies have focused on understanding and measuring the asymmetries in digital development across the European Union (Borowiecki *et al.*, 2021, Kolupaieva & Tiesheva,

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2023, Pinto et al., 2023), in selected groups of EU countries (i.e. Central-Eastern Europe countries) (Tókéš, 2022) or in individual member countries (Kuc-Czarnecka, 2020, Benediktová et al., 2023), there are little up-to-date studies that provide insights into the digital divide in countries forming the so-called Visegrad Group.

For this reason our study aims to analyse and assess the digital divide between the Visegrad countries and the EU-27 countries in the years 2017-2022. To achieve this goal our study is driven by the following research questions: What results did the V4 countries achieve in the years 2017-2022 in terms of digitalization? How did these results compare to other EU countries and what was the scale of the digital divide? Was the digital divide narrowing or widening and in what dimensions considering pre-pandemic period (2017-2019) and pandemic period (2019-2022)? Did the V4 countries show any similarity and differences in terms of the pace and directions of changes in the digital divide in this specific sub-periods?

The studied Visegrad Group (V4) is an informal regional form of cooperation between four Central European countries - the Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, and Slovakia, which are united not only by proximity and similar geopolitical and socio-economic conditions, but above all by common history, tradition and culture. Over the last three decades the Visegrad countries, due to the transformation in the political and economic system and integration with the EU, have undergone a process of rapid socio-economic modernization, including digitalization aspects (Vallušová et al., 2022). This transition makes their digital transformation particularly interesting because it reflects the efforts made by these countries to narrow the digital divide, especially to the EU's digital leaders or the so-called "the Old Union" countries, which is of key importance for their future socio-economic development. The economic growth strategies of V4 countries in recent years was based mostly on the development of low-tech industries and low-knowledge-intensive services, relatively low labour costs, financing of investment from European funds with high dependence on foreign direct investment (Kordalska & Olczyk, 2021, Éltető et al., 2022, Kopiński et al., 2024). These competitive advantages are slowly being exhausted and thus digitalization is seen as a new engine of growth and sustainable development in the V4 countries, contributing to their competitiveness (Błaszczak & Szadurski, 2022).

Our study embodies two main contributions. Firstly, it aims not only to measure and assess the scale of digital divide, but also improves understanding of the specificity of this phenomenon, observed in the V4 countries over recent years, comparing it on the background of the results achieved in the European Union. It allows us to draw conclusions on the scope of digital divide at different levels, as well as to point out similarities and differences between the V4 countries. It also helps researchers to understand what issues need to be addressed in future research. Secondly, by assessing the results of digitalization efforts which were being made in the V4 countries, we point to the factors that contributed to the digital divide. For this reason, our study could be helpful for identifying and developing more coherent frameworks and policies to address the digital divide challenges in these countries, what is important in terms of overcoming digital inequalities.

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To achieve these contributions the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents a literature review on the digital divide, dilemmas related to measuring this phenomenon and research in this field related to the V4 countries. In Section 3 we present the research methodology. Section 4 includes the comparative analyses undertaken on the data collected, using analysis of time trends and cluster analysis. Section 5 presents the discussion of findings. Finally, in Section 6 the final conclusions as well as limitations of the study and recommendations for future research are included.

In order to achieve the aim of this study, a comparative analysis of the performance of the Visegrad countries and the remaining EU countries was carried out based on Eurostat public statistics on the DESI and its four sub-indices. Moreover, to uncover major similarities and contrasts in the digital divide among these countries the Ward method was also used.

2. Literature review

2.1. Digital divide - from Internet access to ICT use outcomes

Research on the digital divide and identification of factors responsible for its emergence, scale and consequences is the subject of many multidisciplinary studies. For this reason, in the light of existing body of literature digital divide appears to be a very complex, dynamic and multidimensional phenomenon, consisting of a set of different divides, caused by a variety of factors (Vassilakopoulou & Hustad, 2021, Aissaoui, 2022). The OECD (2001) defines the digital divide as “the gap between individuals, households, businesses and geographic areas at different socio-economic levels with regard both to their opportunities to access ICT and to their use of the Internet for a wide variety of activities”. Within this context, numerous studies in the last decades have addressed the need to detect, measure and understand existing disparities.

The digital divide takes many forms that can contribute to inequalities in societies and economies. For a comprehensive analysis of this phenomenon researchers use the theory of three levels of digital divide. Initially, the digital divide was understood as a dichotomous situation related to a state of having or not having an access to the Internet with those who had an Internet connection seen as being on the preferred side of the divide (van Dijk, 2005, Riggins & Dewan, 2005, Scheerder et al., 2017). This access divide, has been particularly widely studied from the early 90s until the beginning of the 21st century, when many scholars argued that this concept can't be based solely on the division between having and not having access to ICT (van Dijk, 2020, Lythreatis et al., 2022). The research on this phenomenon evolved, gradually focusing on the reasons underlying the occurrence of disparities in access to and use of ICT (Cruz-Jesus et al., 2012). For this reason in recent years relatively little research has examined the first level digital divide (Van Deursen & Van Dijk, 2019). The experience of the Covid-19 pandemic has shown that access to ICT is still a critical problem in many countries and regions (Lai & Widmar, 2021). However, as broadband Internet access and digital devices are now almost universal in many countries and regions, the issue goes beyond physical and material access and includes factors such as the availability of cutting-edge technologies, reliable high-

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speed internet connections and the affordability of Internet services (Lutz, 2019, Reddick et al., 2024).

Scholars of the second level digital divide claimed that even with universal physical access the divide continues to expand due to diverse modes of use within the group of users of digital devices, which can be attributed to different levels of digital competence (Hargittai & Hinnant, 2008, van Deursen & van Dijk, 2019, Schmoelz, 2023). The new perspective has resulted in a shift towards examining factors such as the inequalities in technical means, autonomy of use, patterns of use, and digital skills (Lythreathis et al., 2022). Research within the second-level divide focuses therefore on two main strands: the first one refers to inequalities among Internet users belonging to different social groups in the way they use ICT (DiMaggio et al., 2004, Hargittai, 2002, Wei, 2012, Büchi et al., 2016, van Deursen & Andrade, 2018), while the second focuses on digital skills as one of the most important factors in conceptualizing the second level digital divide (Mossberger et al., 2003, van Deursen et al., 2016). The Covid-19 pandemic has highlighted the importance of digital skills in the context of existing inequalities and the need to acquire new skills in this field. Moreover, the use of new technologies, such as artificial intelligence, big data, data mining, also requires new competences, which sets new directions for research on the digital divide at this level (Lutz, 2019, van Deursen et al., 2019, Cotter & Reisdorf, 2020).

In recent years, the discourse on the digital divide has expanded to include issues related to the beneficial outcomes of Internet use, which in 2011 were labelled the third-level digital divide (Wei et al., 2012). Researchers studying this form of divide claim that even if the users have the same level of equipment and appropriate skills, they may not get the same returns from their Internet use (van Deursen et al., 2016, Ragnedda, 2016). There are two main approaches to examining the third-level digital divide. The first one examines the relationships between various second-level digital divide factors and offline outcomes (Van Deursen & Helsper, 2015, Scheerder, et al., 2017). The second approach uses capital theory, in particular Bourdieu's theory, to understand the digital divide in terms of economic, social and cultural capital and to demonstrate its relevance in the digital domain (Zhao et al., 2022, Merisalo and Makkonen, 2022, Park & Chun, 2024).

It needs to be highlighted that current understandings of digital divide seem to be not sufficient to explain and address some causes, forms, and consequences of emerging inequalities. Scholars not only propose new aspects of examining the three-level digital divide (Lythreathis et al., 2022, Kovač et al, 2024), but also postulate the introduction of further levels taking into account for example algorithmic awareness (Gran et al., 2021), data inequalities (Cinnamon, 2020) or organizational requirements and support for the access to and competent use of digital technologies (Schmölz et al., 2020, van de Werfhorst et al., 2022).

As the situation within the digital divide, especially the second and the third level, has strong socio-demographic and economic background, a large part of the research concerns the conceptualization of digital divide between individuals or socio-economic groups. In addition to these advances the geographical context of inequalities constitutes a separate line of research,

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as geography has always been considered an important variable. In the spatial context the digital divide is basically considered at two levels. At an international level it shows differences among different countries and at a domestic level it results from differences within a single country. However, there are also other geography-related divides considered: among the developed countries, between the developed and developing countries, between the regions, as well as between the rural and urban areas (Haefner & Sternberg, 2020, Elena-Bucea et al., 2021, Holl & Rama, 2023, Chiesa & Rykkja, 2024). In each of these geographical dimensions digital disparities may occur regarding access to ICT, digital skills and usage patterns as well as ICT usage performance, rooted in differentiated economic, social, political or technical backgrounds.

2.2. Measuring the digital divide

Research conducted for at least two decades has shown that digital divide requires a diverse approach to its measurement (Barzilai-Nahon, 2006; Barzilai-Nahon et al., 2012; Korovkin et al., 2022; Mahdilloo et al., 2023). The primary source of data for analysis is data from official national statistics, collected and processed by organizations such as the ITU (International Telecommunication Union - UN agency), Eurostat, World Bank, OECD and many others, as well as independent surveys. The official statistics collect more and more detailed data on the state of digitization in various aspects and in various breakdowns every year. For example, the ITU collects data for 178 indicators of digitization with additional breakdowns, and Eurostat collects 105 indicators as part of the Digital Economy and Society database. Some organizations, individual researchers or research teams propose a series of indexes for general purposes or to obtain more accurate results of their own research to allow a synthetic assessment of the degree of digitization in different areas using one or more indicators. Examples of such synthetic indices include: The Digitization Index (DiGiX), Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI), ASEAN Digital Integration Index (ADII), Digital Intelligence Index (DII), World Digital Competitiveness (WDC), etc.. These indexes differ substantially in terms of construction, metric used, and the areas they cover. An analysis of selected indices is presented by Choczyńska et al. (2024). Attempts are also made to create indices based on those already existing but requiring a smaller number of indicators while maintaining comparable results – for example, in the case of the DESI index (Bruno et al., 2023). For the purposes of assessments in a narrower scope, covering only selected areas of digitization, specialized indexes are also created, e.g. E-Government Development Index (EGDI), E-Participation Index, Human Capital Index, Digital Readiness Index, etc..

As part of the study of the digital divide level, changes in individual indicators or synthetic indices over time are analysed, their values are compared in a global, national and regional perspective. Various statistical methods are used, such as concentration and regression analysis, including Ginni coefficient analysis (Riccardini & Facio, 2002). A widely used method is clustering, which allows for the creation of groups of entities with the greatest similarity in

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terms of individual indicators or their groups (Cruz-Jesus et al., 2012, Borowiecki et al., 2021, Kolupaieva & Tiesheva, 2023). A special index has also been created to study the digital divide in detail. The Digital Divide Index (DDI) is composed of two scores: the infrastructure/adoption (INFA) score and the socioeconomic (SE) score (Gallardo, 2024).

A comprehensive analysis of digital divide measurement methods is conducted by Barzilai-Nahon (Barzilai-Nahon, 2006). She examined and compared both the methodology of measuring indicators and assessed the synthetic indices used so far. A similar analysis was conducted by Vehovar et al. (Vehovar et al., 2006), who reached a rather controversial conclusion that the measurement methods used may lead to different results and conclusions.

In the European Union, the problem of the digital divide has been addressed by many researchers in recent decades, using a number of the methods mentioned above (Borowiecki et al., 2021, Małkowska et al., 2021, Castillo-Tellez, 2023). One of the proven indices for EU countries is DESI, based on indicators from official statistics of Member States and used in monitoring progress in the field of digital transformation and the digital divide by the European Commission. The European Commission has been publishing annual reports on digitization based on DESI since 2014. Digital divide measurements are made for the internal needs of countries, to illustrate differences in groups of individuals, households and enterprises (Lucendo-Monedero et al., 2019). Based on the research results, local, regional, national and EU policies are also created (Decision 2022/2481; European Commission, 2023) aimed at minimizing the digital divide. This is particularly important for social groups affected by exclusion (de Clercq et al., 2023). Research conducted on the digital divide allows for a better understanding of this phenomenon, determining its scale, identifying possible causes of inequalities in individual countries (Várallyai et al., 2015), analysing policies in the field of digital transformation (Drăgan et al., 2024) and in the field of counteracting digital divide in its various areas, such as e-government (Pérez-Morote et al., 2020) or e-education (Cruz-Jesus et al., 2016).

2.3. Digitalization and the digital divide in the V4 countries

The process of digital transformation and the phenomenon of the digital divide in the Visegrad countries have been a field of research for several years, mainly among researchers from the countries of this group. The research problem appeared both in the perspective of the CEE countries, the V4 group and its individual members.

An interesting field for comparison is the research conducted before the accession to the European Union. Research conducted in 2003-2005 in Hungary (Kiss, 2007) showed a significant digital gap and was a signal that this problem was already noticeable then. The author examines Hungary's accomplishments in digital equity, exploring new ways to bridge the digital divide and address issues of traditional social exclusion in the information society. Research conducted in the following years (2005-2008) in the Czech Republic only confirmed the significance of this problem (Lupáč, Sládek, 2008). In the article “The Deepening of the

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Digital Divide in the Czech Republic” the researchers conclude that the main problems were the lack of public access points or awareness of them, lack of digital skills, and low understanding of the benefits and possibilities of the internet. The demographic distribution of physical access showed that a large part of Czech society, especially older people, those with low education, low income, and limited social contacts, were significantly lagging in the informatization process. As the research showed this gap were widening. However, research conducted in subsequent years (2013) in Hungary regarding digital divide circumstances and factors indicated a significant improvement, especially in access to the internet. At the same time, the authors point to the significant role of European Union funds in reducing this problem. According to the authors, the stratification in the rural/urban division and the exclusion of the elderly remain a significant problem (Várallyai et al., 2015). The problem of exclusion of older people is also pointed out by the authors of studies conducted later in Poland (Adamczyk & Betlej, 2021; Tomczyk et al., 2023). From the point of view of analysing the causes and possibilities of narrowing the digital divide, an important role is played by studies analysing the policies of individual V4 countries in the field of digital transformation, its goals and effects of implementation (Drăgan et al., 2024; Török 2024).

Taking into account the purpose of this paper, comparative studies in which individual V4 countries are assessed in relation to other EU countries or leaders in the field of digitalization are particularly important. Such studies often provide more detailed information on the factors and barriers to digitalization in individual countries. In recent years, comparative studies have been conducted on the level of digitalization in Hungary (Cseh-Zelina, 2023), Poland (Stolarczyk, 2018; Ćwiek, 2018), and Slovakia (Jenčová et al., 2023). In these studies, the authors make extensive use of the DESI Index, which allows for a direct comparison of conclusions for individual countries. A certain benchmark for our research is also provided by those that directly examine the state of digitalization, the process of digital transformation, and the digital divide in the V4 countries and in comparison to the entire EU. Such research has been conducted in recent years by Chetverikova (2023). In this paper, she identifies strengths and weaknesses of digital development of the Visegrad countries that predetermined their “lagging” position. Research conducted by Vallušová et al. (2022) indicates that, to a large extent, the digital lag is due to human capital characteristics: generally lower levels of digital skills in the population (manifested by lower than the EU average levels of human capital in DESI) and greater digital inequalities. DESI indicators were also used by Esses et al. (2021) in research that examines digitalization and sustainability together. An interesting approach was also presented by Kuráková et al. (2021), who use the Digital Divide Index in their analyses, which illustrates the digital divide in a slightly different way than the analysis of differences in DESI indicators. Mészáros (2024) points to the important problem of linking the degree of digitalization with the efficiency of enterprises. The author compares 3 out of 4 V4 countries to the leaders in digitalization: Finland, Denmark and the Netherlands. Valuable conclusions are also provided by research on digital competitiveness in V4 countries in the years 2018-2022 (Čerňanová & Stoviček, 2024). The authors use the IMD index, which measures three main

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factors influencing a country's digital competitiveness (Knowledge, Technology, Future Readiness). In the conclusion they state that bridging the digital divide is important because the state of digitalization of a country can be an important factor of its competitiveness. An even longer research period was adopted by (Ragnedda & Kreitem, 2018) who examined the level of the Digital Divide in 11 countries of the former Eastern Bloc in the years 2007–2018. In their research, they distinguished three levels of the digital divide and made comparisons between countries and in relation to the EU28 average. In general, it can be stated that the research conducted so far indicates a still significant scale of the digital divide in the Visegrad countries, but also the existing disproportions between these countries in terms of different levels of this divide and the pace of digital transformation.

3. Research methodology

To give an overview of the digital divide across Visegrad countries, we have analyzed the data on the Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) and its four sub-indices. These data has been used to measure and track changes in the digital divide in the Visegrad Countries in comparison to other European Union countries and to compare and contrast similarities and differences regarding changes in this phenomenon at its different levels. The analysis was based on data from 2017 to 2022 covering 27 countries of the European Union. The basic data source was the data available on the European Union website in the Eurostat database [Kowalik et al., 2024]. The DESI has a three-level structure consisting of dimensions, subdimensions and indicators. In our analysis, we focused on the DESI and its four highest level dimensions (sub-indices) that make up the total DESI index. The DESI is calculated as a weighted sum, using the weights associated with each dimension, sub-dimension and indicator. Each of the sub-indices analysed has the same weight attributed (25%) (European Commission, 2022c). The choice of the DESI index with its four sub-indices as a measure of the digital divide was determined by the aim of our study and several other substantive reasons. The use of indices like DESI makes it possible to summarize complex and multidimensional phenomena which is digital development and therefore enables the assessment of the associated divide. Such indices are also relatively easy to interpret and allow for easier tracking of changes over time periods (Cruz-Jesus et al., 2012; Mahdiloo et al., 2023, Bruno et al., 2023). DESI is a proper measure not only to assess performance and progress recorded in individual countries, but also to present a comparative analysis across EU countries indicating areas where there is improvement potential in individual countries. And thus this index can be seen as very useful to formulate recommendations for relevant policy areas (European Commission, 2022c).

An in-depth analysis of indicators used to calculate the DESI showed that they allow to obtain multifaceted data on digital divide, as they examine different factors affecting the degree of digitalization, indicated in the literature (Haefner & Sternberg, 2020, van Deursen et al., 2019, Lutz, 2019, Cotter & Reisdorf, 2020, Reddick et al., 2024). DESI extends the primary domains of the digital divide such as access and skills by including indicators related to the mobile and fixed broadband coverage, take-up and price indexes, as well as indicators related

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to Internet users skills and advanced skills and development, also addressing gender issues. Moreover, it takes into account the digital transformation of the business sector, including not only indicators assessing the scale of e-commerce and the up-take of the already well-known technologies, but also those relating to the Industry 4.0 such as AI, Cloud and Big Data. Finally, it evaluates the digital penetration in the public administration by using Digital Public Services indicators. For this reason the DESI may be used to measure the digital divide of the first level (access/capacity/affordability) and second level (Internet user skills, advanced skills and development, ICT usage in business and public sector). However, it is not a measure of the third-level divide as it doesn't measure the offline effects achieved in studied countries thanks to the use of ICT. Moreover, the methodology of DESI is discussed and agreed under the Digital Single Market Strategic Group, which makes it reliable for this specific subset of countries (EU countries). Considering that the EU has a unified statistics system and data collection and calculation process for all EU member states, including Visegrad countries, those data can be seen as fairly well harmonized, suitable and reliable for achieving the objectives of our study. Its usefulness is also confirmed by research of other authors (Laitsou et al., 2020, Borowiecki et al., 2021, Olczyk & Kuc-Czarnecka, 2022, Bruno et al., 2023).

The research was conducted using different methods. The data on the DESI index and its four sub-indices with descriptive statistics and basic measures of time series dynamics, i.e., absolute annual increment were used to determine the level of digitalization and dynamics of changes in index values. At the same time this allowed us to assess the scale of the digital divide, the pace of its change and to point the dimensions in which it occurred. The data descriptions include several comparative breakdowns: a general description of the data for Visegrad countries, yearly trend analysis and a comparison with the EU27 and Finland, which had the highest DESI score in any of the marginal years of analysis.

To classify countries in terms of the similarity of changes in the value and structure of the DESI index, a cluster analysis was used, which is one of the basic methods of so-called unsupervised grouping (Everitt et al., 2001). Cluster analysis includes methods of multidimensional statistical analysis, which enable to extract homogeneous subsets of objects of the population studied. The basis for the designation of groups (clusters) are the variables that characterize the analysed objects. This method uses measures of discrepancy or distance between objects when forming clusters. The most direct way to calculate the distance between objects in a multidimensional space is to calculate the Euclidean distance, however a different metric can be considered as a measure of distance. It is also possible to estimate the distance of objects without using a metric. Our research uses the most widespread hierarchical clustering method - the Ward method, which takes a variance analysis approach to estimate the distance between the focus (Murtagh & Legendre, 2014). This method aims to minimize the sum of squared deviations of any two clusters that can be formed at any stage of the algorithm (Ward, 1963). The applied method is considered one of the best methods of cluster analysis, due to its effectiveness in reproducing the real structure of data and creating clusters of similar numbers. However, it aims to form clusters of relatively small size. The principle of this method is not

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optimization, but minimization of heterogeneity (Majerova & Nevima, 2017). For this reason it aims to find the greatest similarity between objects, what was important from the point of view of objectives of our study. No significant linear relationships between the different variables were found for the data considered. The selection of the number of clusters was based on the difference between the maximum similarity within the groups and the minimum (Kaufmann & Rousseeuw, 1990). On this basis, an optimal number of concentrations of four was established. Cluster analysis was carried out with the use of the Statgraphics 18 program. Figures were prepared with the use of Excel.

Our analyses covered the years 2017-2022, but due to the specific nature of this period, i.e. the fact that it covered the period of the Covid-19 pandemic, which significantly influenced the digitalization efforts taken in individual countries, we divided this period for two subperiods covering the years 2017-2019 and 2019-2022. This approach allowed for capturing the average annual pace of changes in individual EU countries, including the V4 countries, and their specificity in the pre-pandemic period (2017-2019), and then in the pandemic period (2019-2022).

4. Results

4.1. Comparative analysis on digitalization and digital divide in Visegrad countries in the years 2017-2022

This section describes Digital Economy and Society Index provided by DESI database. The discussion focuses on the four (4) main sub-indices that are Human Capital, Connectivity, Integration of Digital Technology and Digital Public Services of EU27 and Visegrad countries. Data descriptions are divided into several comparisons which include the overall data description of Visegrad, yearly trend analysis and comparison with EU27 and Finland, which had the highest DESI score in any of the marginal years of analysis. The overall data as displayed in Table 1 consists of 162 observations for EU27 and 24 observations for Visegrad that covers 2017 to 2022. The overall data from EU27 can be described as normally distributed with mean and median are close to each other for all the four (4) sub-indices. Further, the skewness and kurtosis supported the data normality that is close to 0 and 3 respectively. Similarly, for Visegrad countries, despite for human capital with slightly thin distribution of tails, all the four (4) sub-indices imply data uses in the study are normally distributed.

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Table 1. Descriptive Statistics of EU-27

Variable	N	Min	Mean	p50	Max	Range	Skewness	Kurtosis
Human Capital	162	34.35	57.06	55.34	89.24	54.89	0.36	2.66
Connectivity	162	15.84	47.02	44.68	96.36	80.52	0.65	3.10
Integration of Digital Technology	162	12.65	36.87	35.84	73.86	61.21	0.42	2.98
Digital Public Services	162	9.27	71.63	73.07	113.97	104.71	-0.47	3.14

Source: own elaboration based on DESI data

The six years data exhibits in Table 2 indicates a consistent increase of Human Capital from 2017 to 2022 with moderate variation throughout the years. Connectivity also shows an increasing trend with some variability in distribution. Aligned with the previous two sub-indices, Integration of Digital Technology and Digital Public Services exhibit increasing trend but with notable and substantial variability. The findings imply a temporal trend with an upward trend across all indicators from 2017 to 2022.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics of EU-27 by Year

Variable	Year	N	Min	Mean	p50	Max	Range	Skewness	Kurtosis
Human Capital	2017	27	34.87	54.20	51.33	80.83	45.96	0.39	2.63
Connectivity	2017	27	15.84	33.47	32.60	49.32	33.48	0.12	2.41
Integration of Digital Technology	2017	27	12.65	28.65	28.50	44.07	31.42	-0.06	2.21
Digital Public Services	2017	27	9.27	59.03	58.00	83.91	74.64	-0.76	3.41
Human Capital	2018	27	34.35	54.84	51.56	82.39	48.05	0.38	2.68
Connectivity	2018	27	16.75	35.71	35.06	51.19	34.44	0.01	2.58
Integration of Digital Technology	2018	27	14.27	31.54	31.10	48.55	34.28	-0.09	2.29
Digital Public Services	2018	27	12.26	64.15	63.68	90.07	77.82	-0.77	3.40
Human Capital	2019	27	34.97	56.36	53.72	82.22	47.26	0.23	2.36
Connectivity	2019	27	20.36	40.42	40.99	54.87	34.51	-0.14	2.70
Integration of Digital Technology	2019	27	15.09	34.52	34.12	53.66	38.57	-0.07	2.31
Digital Public Services	2019	27	14.79	68.34	68.73	95.01	80.22	-0.80	3.51
Human Capital	2020	27	35.66	57.63	54.63	84.36	48.70	0.26	2.56
Connectivity	2020	27	23.93	45.70	45.20	60.03	36.10	-0.31	2.55
Integration of Digital Technology	2020	27	16.39	38.10	37.62	61.25	44.86	0.05	2.36

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Digital Public Services	2020	27	18.62	73.48	73.29	101.01	82.39	-0.80	3.51
Human Capital	2021	27	37.59	58.76	55.57	88.16	50.57	0.41	2.85
Connectivity	2021	27	38.89	56.22	55.23	90.14	51.25	1.09	4.10
Integration of Digital Technology	2021	27	17.61	42.20	42.16	66.76	49.15	0.05	2.44
Digital Public Services	2021	27	22.71	79.51	79.65	107.82	85.12	-0.83	3.56
Human Capital	2022	27	38.65	60.57	57.43	89.24	50.59	0.33	2.52
Connectivity	2022	27	49.78	70.60	70.58	96.36	46.58	0.38	2.82
Integration of Digital Technology	2022	27	18.94	46.22	45.91	73.86	54.92	0.09	2.59
Digital Public Services	2022	27	26.30	85.26	84.88	113.97	87.67	-0.82	3.50
Human Capital	Total	162	34.35	57.06	55.34	89.24	54.89	0.36	2.66
Connectivity	Total	162	15.84	47.02	44.68	96.36	80.52	0.65	3.10
Integration of Digital Technology	Total	162	12.65	36.87	35.84	73.86	61.21	0.42	2.98
Digital Public Services	Total	162	9.27	71.63	73.07	113.97	104.71	-0.47	3.14

Source: own elaboration based on DESI data

The data suggest major improvements in Human Capital, Connectivity, Integration of Digital Technology and Digital Public Services regardless of different group of countries, the EU27 and the Visegrad countries. Notably, Finland outperformed in all areas sets as leader in digital infrastructure, skilled workforce and comprehensive digital public services.

Table 3 and 4 displays the four (4) main sub-indices for Visegrad Group (V4) and individual countries. The mean value of 2017 to 2022 is compared and tested for the mean different with EU27 and Finland (FI) respectively. Table 5 to Table 8 segregate the sub-indices for 2 period segments that is from 2017 to 2019 and 2020 to 2022 in comparison to EU27 and Finland respectively.

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Table 3. Mean Value of Digitization sub-indices for Visegrad Countries in Comparison to EU27 for 2017 to 2022

Sub-Indices (2017 - 2022)	EU27	V4		CZ	HU		PL		SK	
1_Human Capital	54.28	48.68	***	53.86	46.48	***	43.11	***	51.25	*
2_Connectivity	46.10	42.55		40.97	48.01		38.96		42.27	
3_Integration of Digital Technology	35.71	26.99	**	35.34	20.77	***	22.15	***	29.69	*
4_Digital Public Services	70.93	58.99	**	65.89	58.80	**	55.87	**	55.38	**

Note: ***, **, * represent the mean different test between V4 countries and EU27 are significant at 1%, 5% and 10% level respectively.

Source: own elaboration based on DESI data

Table 4. Mean Value of Digitization sub-indices for Visegrad Countries in Comparison to Finland for 2017 to 2022

Sub-Indices (2017 - 2022)	FI	V4		CZ	HU		PL		SK	
1_Human Capital	84.53	48.68	***	53.86	46.48	***	43.11	***	51.25	***
2_Connectivity	49.54	42.55		40.97	48.01		38.96		42.27	
3_Integration of Digital Technology	57.85	26.99	***	35.34	20.77	***	22.15	***	29.69	***
4_Digital Public Services	94.37	58.99	***	65.89	58.80	***	55.87	***	55.38	***

Note: ***, **, * represent the mean different test between V4 countries and Finland are significant at 1%, 5% and 10% level respectively.

Source: own elaboration based on DESI data

Table 5. Mean Value of Digitization sub-indices for Visegrad Countries in Comparison to EU27 for 2017 to 2019

Sub-Indices (2017 - 2019)	EU27	V4		CZ	HU		PL		SK	
1_Human Capital	52.58	46.78	***	51.98	45.36	***	41.21	***	48.58	**
2_Connectivity	34.16	32.57		31.96	35.74		29.10		33.50	
3_Integration of Digital Technology	30.55	23.32	**	30.33	17.95	***	18.30	***	26.71	
4_Digital Public Services	63.18	51.62	**	57.75	51.89	**	47.78	**	49.07	**

Note: ***, **, * represent the mean different test between V4 countries and EU27 are significant at 1%, 5% and 10% level respectively.

Source: own elaboration based on DESI data

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Table 6. Mean Value of Digitization sub-indices for Visegrad Countries in Comparison to Finland for 2017 to 2019

Sub-Indices (2017 - 2019)	FI	V4		CZ		HU		PL		SK	
1_Human Capital	81.81	46.78	***	51.98	***	45.36	***	41.21	***	48.58	***
2_Connectivity	38.12	32.57		31.96		35.74		29.10	*	33.50	
3_Integration of Digital Technology	48.40	23.32	***	30.33	**	17.95	***	18.30	***	26.71	***
4_Digital Public Services	85.61	51.62	***	57.75	***	51.89	***	47.78	***	49.07	***

Note: ***, **, * represent the mean different test between V4 countries and Finland are significant at 1%, 5% and 10% level respectively.

Source: own elaboration based on DESI data

Table 7. Mean Value of Digitization sub-indices for Visegrad Countries in Comparison to EU27 for 2020 to 2022

Sub-Indices (2020 - 2022)	EU27	V4		CZ		HU		PL		SK	
1_Human Capital	55.98	50.57	***	55.73		47.61	***	45.02	***	53.92	
2_Connectivity	58.05	52.53		49.99		60.28		48.82		51.03	
3_Integration of Digital Technology	40.86	30.65	**	40.35		23.59	***	26.00	**	32.66	*
4_Digital Public Services	78.67	66.35	**	74.03		65.72	*	63.96	**	61.69	**

Note: ***, **, * represent the mean different test between V4 countries and Finland are significant at 1%, 5% and 10% level respectively.

Source: own elaboration based on DESI data

Table 8. Mean Value of Digitization Sub-indices for Visegrad Countries in Comparison to Finland for 2020 to 2022

Sub-Indices (2020 - 2022)	FI	V4		CZ		HU		PL		SK	
1_Human Capital	87.25	50.57	***	55.73	***	47.61	***	45.02	***	53.92	***
2_Connectivity	60.96	52.53		49.99		60.28		48.82		51.03	
3_Integration of Digital Technology	67.29	30.65	***	40.35	**	23.59	***	26.00	***	32.66	***
4_Digital Public Services	103.14	66.35	***	74.03	***	65.72	***	63.96	***	61.69	***

Note: ***, **, * represent the mean different test between V4 countries and Finland are significant at 1%, 5% and 10% level respectively.

Source: own elaboration based on DESI data

With respect to Human Capital dimension country comparison portrays an increasing trend of all indicators for all EU27 countries that is also true for Visegrad countries. Finland shows the best Human Capital index with the greatest mean (84.53) among EU27. The statistics also

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provide indications that Netherland, Belgium, Estonia, Malta, Portugal and Sweden have a notable improvement in human capital throughout the years. Meanwhile, among Visegrad countries, Czech Republic has the highest mean Human Capital, followed closely by Slovakia, Hungary and Poland. Czech Republic consistently ranks highest, indicating strong educational and skill development outcome. Distribution ranges from Czech Republic and Poland indicating substantial variability and at the same time proposes greater chances for Poland to invest further in human capital. Comparison of the four (4) Visegrad countries with EU27 discloses these four (4) countries have significantly lower Human Capital index relative to EU27. The mean difference is significant at 1% level. Comparison for individual Visegrad country with EU27 are very similar with the group comparison but interestingly, the mean difference of Human Capital for Czech Republic is not statistically significant. This imply although Czech Republic have lower Human Capital index in comparison to EU27 but the gap is not substantial.

In respective of Connectivity, the statistics show an increasing trend over the years, with some variability in distribution. There is notable increasing trend in Connectivity within the 6-year period with mean score more than doubling over this period. This indicates significant improvements in digital infrastructure and access across 2017 to 2022. Denmark has the highest mean score suggest the best connectivity among all other EU27. It is also crucial to note, other than Denmark, countries that have outstanding improvement in Connectivity index includes Cyprus, Germany, France, Ireland and Italy. Across Visegrad countries, Hungary with the highest mean (48.01) outperformed the other three (3) countries. Hungary leads in connectivity reflecting better infrastructure investment on digital connectivity. The mean difference test between Visegrad and EU27 reveals although Visegrad countries have lower Connectivity index but the difference is not statistically significant. Surprisingly, Hungary is not only outcast the other Visegrad countries, but in comparison to EU27, the mean value for Hungary is slightly greater than EU27. On the contrary, Poland with the lowest mean connectivity (38.96), infer great potential of further improvement in infrastructure investment. Connectivity is found to varies among countries but Visegrad countries are generally competitive with EU27.

Similar to other sub-indices discussed earlier, there is clear evidence of increasing trend of Integration of Digital Technology in EU27 and Visegrad countries. As recorded in EU27 statistics, there is notable variability of Integration of Digital Technology from 2017 (28.65) to 2022 (46.22) in the mean score. It is a good indicator that portrays serious initiative by each country to promote integration using digital technology. While Finland leads in Human Capital and Denmark leads in Connectivity, these two (2) countries consistently display the highest Integration of Digital Technology among EU27 with the mean score of 57.84 and 56.35 respectively. Except Denmark, Finland and Sweden, there are lack of evidence to identify countries with substantial improvement of Integration of Digital Technology in Europe. Between the four (4) Visegrad countries, the greatest Integration of Digital Technology belongs

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to Czech Republic with mean score of 35.34 followed by Slovakia (29.69), Poland (22.15) and Hungary (20.77). The mean difference comparison of Integration of Digital Technology between Visegrad countries and EU27 discloses Visegrad countries have statistically lower integration relative to EU27. Except for Czech Republic, all other Visegrad countries are statistically having lower index than EU27. This is mainly contributed by higher technology adoption rate in Czech Republic. Despite, these countries are still far lagging from Finland (57.85) with statistically lower Integration of Digital Technology index. The variation of integration level in Europe suggests varying levels of technological adoption and infrastructure between countries. These findings document the importance of targeted policy intervention to bridge gaps of Visegrad countries and the EU benchmarks in the area of digital technology integration.

The descriptive statistics of Digital Public Services depict consistent upward trends of countries in EU27 as well as in Visegrad countries. Mean value of Digital Public Services soar from 59.03 in 2017 to 46.22 in 2022. The trend indicates steady development in Digital Public Services from 2017 to 2022 reflecting enhanced efficiency and accessibility of public service through digital platforms. The greatest mean score of Digital Public Services among EU27 goes to Estonia at 98.63, followed by Finland (94.37) and Malta (92.38). The distribution ranges between countries indicating substantial variability. Across Visegrad countries, once again Czech Republic also leads in Digital Public Services with mean score of 65.89 suggesting efficient public service digitalization. Hungary followed closely behind with mean value of 58.80 while Poland and Slovakia score 55.87 and 55.38 of mean respectively. The gap scores between individual Visegrad country suggests disparities in digital service delivery capabilities and infrastructure. Visegrad countries comparison with EU27 reveals significant mean differences of Visegrad group as well as Visegrad individual country. However, findings for Czech Republic discover no evidence of significant difference between the country and EU27 in term of Public Digital Services. Digital Public Services in Czech Republic generally match or closely approaching those in EU27, indicating effective digital transformation in public service sectors. The gap is even more pronounced when compared to Finland, which has one of the most advanced digital public service infrastructures in Europe. Finland's high scores in this area indicate a mature e-government ecosystem, with widespread access to digital services and robust open data initiatives. The V4 countries, in contrast, are significantly behind, highlighting a need for strategic investments and reforms in public sector digitalization.

4.2. Changes in the digitalization level and the digital divide in Visegrad countries in the years 2017-2019

In order to obtain an in-depth assessment of the change that has occurred in the Visegrad countries in terms of digitalization level and the associated digital divide in the analysed sub-

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periods, using the Ward method, we have carried out an analysis of the average annual absolute increment of the DESI index and its sub-indices. The aim of this analysis was to identify countries characterized by similar structure of changes of the analysed variables and to determine what development patterns in the field of digitalization were followed by the V4 countries and which countries they were similar to. To deepen the conclusions, we have also analysed how was the progress of the V4 countries against the background of the average cluster results and the average results of the EU-27. Based on the output DESI and sub-indices data we have also assessed how the digital divide (calculated as the difference between the average results of the EU-27 or the digital leader and the results of individual V4 countries) changed in the analysed sub-periods. Analyses performed allowed us to evaluate the digitalization efforts of the V4 countries aimed at narrowing the digital divide at its different levels.

In each of the analysed subperiods, i.e. the pre-pandemic period covering years 2017-2019 and the pandemic period covering years 2019-2022 among the EU countries 4 groups of countries were distinguished. The dendrogram showing the results of cluster analysis for the pre-pandemic period is presented in Figure 1 and the average performance for isolated clusters is included in Table 9.

Figure 1. Ward’s dendrogram for the EU-27 Member States for the pre-pandemic period.

Source: Our own study.

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Table 9. The average performance of clusters isolated for the pre-pandemic period

Cluster	Members	Human capital	Connectivity	Integration of digital technology	Digital public services	DESI
1	Austria, Czechia , Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Lithuania, Poland , Slovenia, Spain, Sweden	0,186	0,849	0,677	1,058	2,7700
2	Belgium, Croatia, Estonia, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Slovakia	0,430	0,360	0,619	0,895	2,3036
3	Bulgaria, Cyprus, Greece, Hungary , Latvia, Romania	0,033	0,608	0,378	0,761	1,7794
4	Italy, Portugal	0,193	1,209	0,558	0,795	2,7547

Source: Our own study

In the years 2017-2019, i.e. before the Covid-19 pandemic, the V4 countries were included in three different clusters showing similarity of changes: the Czech Republic and Poland were included in cluster 1, Slovakia – in cluster 2, and Hungary – in cluster 3.

Compared to other clusters, cluster 1 was characterized by, on average, the highest average annual absolute increment of the overall level of digitalization (measured by DESI) and sub-indices in the dimensions of Integration of Digital Technology and Digital Public Services. It also grouped countries that achieved, on average, the second highest annual progress in the Connectivity and the second lowest in the Human Capital dimension. The average characteristics of this cluster were higher than the average annual performance recorded for the EU-27. Such results clearly indicate that in the pre-pandemic period, both the Czech Republic and Poland were among the countries where, over the following years, on average, there was the largest annual progress in the general level of digitalization and the absorption of digital technologies in the business sector, as well as in public services, with at the same time slightly worse progress in access to ICT, as well as significantly worse results compared to other EU countries in terms of improving parameters related to the basic and advanced digital competences of citizens. In terms of the structure of changes in these indicators, the Czech Republic and Poland were similar to many EU-14 countries: Austria, France, Germany and listed in the EU's top ten of DESI ranking in 2017: Finland, Denmark, Sweden, Ireland and Spain, as well as post-socialist countries such as Slovenia and Lithuania.

The Czech Republic achieved above-average or close to the cluster's average results in all dimensions of digitalization except Integration of Digital Technology, in which its results were also lower than the average annual absolute increment recorded for the EU-27 (table 10). In turn, Poland showed worse results than the cluster's and EU-27 average in terms of the average annual absolute increment of DESI value and sub-indices in the dimensions of Connectivity and Integration of Digital Technology. In the latter dimension its results deviated

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significantly from both average values. This pace of change meant that in 2019, compared to 2017, the Czech Republic narrowed the digital divide in relation to the EU-27 average in general and in each of the dimensions of digitalization except for Integration of Digital Technology, in which it lost its advantage over the EU-27 average performance. Poland reduced the divide in relation to the EU-27 average in the area of Human Capital and Digital Public Services, with the Connectivity gap remaining essentially unchanged. Moreover, in the analysed period, both countries achieved a higher average annual absolute increment in the Human Capital dimension than Finland, included in the same cluster, which resulted in narrowing the digital divide in this area also in relation to the leader of the DESI ranking. The Czech Republic managed to reduce the gap with Finland also in the dimension of digitalization of public services.

The third country of the Visegrad Group - Slovakia - was included in cluster 2, alongside highly digitally developed countries such as the Netherlands, Luxembourg, Malta and Estonia, as well as those with a slightly lower level of digitalization such as Belgium or Croatia. In terms of its average characteristics, this cluster stood out from others with the highest average annual absolute increment in the Human Capital dimension and the second highest in the Integration of Digital Technology and Digital Public Services dimensions, while it recorded the second lowest results in the DESI value, and the lowest in the Connectivity dimension. These characteristics only in the Human Capital dimension were higher than the average annual absolute increment recorded in the EU-27. Although Slovakia achieved results below the average values for the cluster, in the Human Capital dimension its average annual absolute increment was significantly above that recorded for the EU-27, as well as the leader of the DESI ranking - Finland, which allowed for narrowing the digital divide that existed in this area in the analysed period (Table 10). In other dimensions and in relation to the overall level of digitalization, the pace of change in Slovakia was significantly lower than in the EU-27 and Finland, and therefore the gaps in this areas (and especially the access divide) have increased compared to 2017. So it can be concluded that in the pre-pandemic period in Slovakia only the digital skills gap was narrowed, while the other divides, especially the one related to access, widened.

The last country - Hungary - was included in cluster 3, which grouped countries ranked lowest in 2017 in terms of the overall digitalization level, with the exception of Latvia (10th place in DESI ranking). The countries grouped in this cluster were characterized by the lowest (or almost the lowest) average annual absolute increment of indices in all the areas studied, which were also lower than those recorded for the EU-27. Compared to the average results of the cluster, Hungary achieved higher average annual absolute increment in the Connectivity and Digital Public Services dimension, as well as in terms of the overall DESI value. At the same time it recorded lower average annual positive change in the Integration of Digital Technology dimension, and performed worst compared to the cluster countries in the Human Capital dimension (table 10). When comparing the average annual absolute increment in Hungary and in the EU-27, Hungary outperformed only in the Connectivity dimension, while in other areas the increment was lower. The progress in the Integration of Digital Technology

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and Human Capital dimensions were particularly negative on this background. This pace of changes meant that in 2019, compared to 2017, Hungary increased its lead over the EU-27 average in Connectivity, while in other areas and in relation to the results of the digital leader - Finland, the gap in general and in all dimensions analysed increased.

The overall picture of the results in the pre-pandemic period is completed by cluster 4, which included only 2 countries - Italy and Portugal, which, compared to the three previous clusters, stood out with the highest pace of changes in the Connectivity area, the second highest scores in the Human Capital dimension and in terms of the overall DESI value, as well as the second lowest scores in the areas of Integration of Digital Technology and Digital Public Services, which in these two latter dimensions were below the average annual absolute increment recorded for the EU-27.

Table 10. Selected characteristics on the performance of V4 countries in the period 2017-2019

Country	HC	Conn.	IoDT	DPS	DESI	HC	Conn.	IoDT	DPS	DESI
	The ratio of the average annual absolute increment of the index in a country to the average annual absolute increment of the index for the cluster (%)					The ratio of the average annual absolute increment of the index in a country to the average annual absolute increment of the index for the EU-27 (%)				
Czechia	155,0	100,4	59,1	107,4	96,6	176,8	117,1	62,9	121,2	108,6
Hungary	9,1	123,8	88,7	114,4	110,2	1,8	103,4	52,7	92,8	79,6
Poland	115,6	85,7	73,5	92,9	87,5	131,9	100,0	78,3	104,9	98,4
Slovakia	69,1	59,5	76,6	83,6	75,3	182,2	29,5	74,6	79,8	70,4
	Change in the divide between the EU-27 performance and country's performance in 2019 compared to 2017					Change in the divide in 2019 compared to 2017: (-) reduction; (+) increase				
Czechia	-0,2505	-0,2487	0,4717	-0,3976	-0,4252	(-)	(-)	(+)	(-)	(-)
Hungary	0,3200	-0,0499	0,6016	0,1342	1,0059	(+)	(-)	(+)	(+)	(+)
Poland	-0,1039	0,0002	0,2766	-0,0917	0,0812	(-)	(+)	(+)	(-)	(+)
Slovakia	-0,2680	1,0268	0,3233	0,3779	1,4600	(-)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)
	Change in the divide between Finland's performance and country's performance in 2019 compared to 2017					Change in the divide in 2019 compared to 2017: (-) reduction; (+) increase				
Czechia	-0,2969	0,0316	1,3338	-0,1306	0,9380	(-)	(+)	(+)	(-)	(+)
Hungary	0,2737	0,2304	1,4638	0,4012	2,3691	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)
Poland	-0,1503	0,2805	1,1387	0,1754	1,4444	(-)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)
Slovakia	-0,3144	1,3071	1,1854	0,6450	2,8232	(-)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)

Source: own elaboration based on DESI data

Summarizing the results in the pre-pandemic period, it can be concluded that the Czech Republic and Poland achieved similar results in this period in terms of the pace and structure of changes in the analysed digitalization indices. The other two countries followed slightly

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different digital development paths, which resulted in different results. The best results were achieved by the Czech Republic, which managed to narrow the digital divide with respect to the EU27 average score in all dimensions except Integration of Digital Technology, in which it lost the advantage over the UE-27 average performance. Slightly worse results were achieved by the other V4 countries: Poland managed to narrow the gap in two dimensions (HC and DPS), maintaining the status quo in terms of Connectivity, while Slovakia and Hungary only in one (in the HC and Connectivity dimension respectively). It is noteworthy that as many as three of the four countries analysed narrowed the digital skills gap, and two countries improved their performance in terms of ICT access and the digitalization of public services. However, the only area, where there was an increase in the divide in each country, was the Integration of Digital Technology dimension.

4.3. Changes in the digitalization level and the digital divide in Visegrad countries in the years 2019-2022

Considering the results achieved during the pandemic period the Visegrad countries were assigned to two different clusters: the Czech Republic and Poland were included in cluster 1, while Slovakia and Hungary were grouped in cluster 2. The dendrogram showing the results of cluster analysis for the pandemic period is presented in Figure 2 and the average performance for isolated clusters is included in Table 11.

Figure 2. Ward’s dendrogram for the EU-27 Member States for the pandemic period.

Source: Our own study.

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Table 11. The average performance of clusters isolated for the pandemic period

Cluster	Members	Human capital	Connectivity	Integration of digital technology	Digital public services	DESI
1	Austria, Belgium, Croatia, Cyprus, Czechia , France, Italy, Malta, Poland , Slovenia, Spain	0,190	2,149	0,835	1,160	4,3344
2	Bulgaria, Germany, Greece, Hungary , Romania, Slovakia	0,220	2,184	0,453	0,897	3,7535
3	Denmark, Finland, Ireland, Netherlands, Sweden	0,429	2,408	1,152	1,270	5,2591
4	Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Portugal	0,403	1,106	0,682	1,192	3,3837

Source: Our own study

Compared to the other clusters, cluster 1 was characterized by the second highest average annual absolute increment related to the overall level of digitalization (measured by the DESI) and in the Integration of Digital Technology dimension, as well as the second lowest results in the Connectivity and Digital Public Services dimensions. It also grouped countries that achieved, on average, the lowest average annual absolute increment of the Human Capital sub-index. The comparison of average values for the cluster and the EU-27 shows that only in the dimensions of Integration of Digital Technology and Digital Public Services the cluster's values were higher. Our analysis indicates that in the pandemic period both the Czech Republic and Poland showed a similar pattern of changes in the field of digitalization. They were among the countries in which in the three consecutive years (2020, 2021 and 2022) there was a higher increase in the value of indicators showing the general digitalization level and the absorption of digital technologies in the business sector compared to the countries of clusters 2 and 4, with at the same time less progress in dimensions related to ICT access and digital public services, as well as definitely the lowest average pace of changes in the digital skills dimension. In terms of the structure of changes in digitalization in the analysed period, the Czech Republic and Poland were again similar to many EU countries: Austria, France, Italy and Spain, belonging to the “Old Union”, as well as Croatia, Slovenia, Cyprus and Malta.

The area in which both the Czech Republic and Poland showed an above-average annual absolute increment in relation to the cluster's average results was the Human Capital dimension, while the dimension that stood out negatively in both countries was the Integration of Digital Technology, and – in the case of Poland – also the Connectivity dimension. The other results of both countries were quite close to the average characteristics of the cluster (Table 12). With such a pace of change in the analysed indices in the Czech Republic, the average annual absolute increment only in the area of Digital Public Services was higher than in the EU-27, while in other areas it was in the range of 80 - 90% of its value. For this reason, this was the only dimension in which the divide with the EU27 average performance narrowed in 2022 compared

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to 2019. With regard to Poland's performance, a higher average annual absolute increment than in the EU-27 was recorded in the Human Capital and Digital Public Services dimensions, which translated into the slightly reduction of the digital divide in both areas. With regard to the digital leader Finland, the digital gap in both countries has increased in each of the areas analysed. This was due to the fact that Finland belonged in this period to the cluster of countries with the highest average annual absolute increments of all indices analysed, recording progress significantly higher than the Czech Republic and Poland.

Table 12. Selected characteristics on the performance of V4 countries in the period 2019-2022

Country	HC	Conn.	IoDT	DPS	DESI	HC	Conn.	IoDT	DPS	DESI
	The ratio of the average annual absolute increment of the index in a country to the average annual absolute increment of the index for the cluster (%)					The ratio of the average annual absolute increment of the index in a country to the average annual absolute increment of the index for the EU-27 (%)				
Czechia	114,7	91,0	78,2	99,9	92,0	90,0	80,0	85,8	105,8	87,7
Hungary	75,8	99,0	110,6	114,6	102,8	68,8	88,5	65,8	93,9	84,9
Poland	136,8	78,2	62,2	97,5	82,9	107,4	68,7	68,2	103,3	79,0
Slovakia	156,7	84,2	89,4	90,3	90,5	142,4	75,2	53,2	73,9	74,8
	Change in the divide between the EU-27 performance and country's performance in 2022 compared to 2019					Change in the divide in 2022 compared to 2019: (-) reduction; (+) increase				
Czechia	0,0727	1,4655	0,3248	-0,1892	1,6739	(+)	(+)	(+)	(-)	(+)
Hungary	0,2263	0,8461	0,7814	0,2015	2,0554	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)
Poland	-0,0536	2,2937	0,7271	-0,1068	2,8604	(-)	(+)	(+)	(-)	(+)
Slovakia	-0,3078	1,8193	1,0692	0,8567	3,4373	(-)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)
	Change in the divide between Finland's performance and country's performance in 2022 compared to 2019					Change in the divide in 2022 compared to 2019: (-) reduction; (+) increase				
Czechia	0,7492	0,4409	2,0806	0,2277	3,4984	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)
Hungary	0,9029	-0,1785	2,5372	0,6184	3,8799	(+)	(-)	(+)	(+)	(+)
Poland	0,6230	1,2691	2,4829	0,3100	4,6850	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)
Slovakia	0,3687	0,7947	2,8250	1,2735	5,2619	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)

Source: own elaboration based on DESI data

In the pandemic period Hungary and Slovakia were included in cluster 2, showing similarity in terms of digital changes to countries such as Bulgaria, Romania, Greece and Germany. With regard to its average characteristics, this cluster stood out from others with the second highest average annual absolute increment in the Connectivity dimension and the second lowest average annual change in the overall digitalization level and in the Human Capital dimension. Moreover, it recorded the lowest average annual increases of sub-indices in the Integration of

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Digital Technology and Digital Public Services dimensions. All these characteristics were lower than the average results recorded for the EU-27.

The only area in which Slovakia showed an above-average annual growth in relation to the cluster's average results was the Human Capital dimension, in other areas it achieved results in the range of 84.2 - 90.5% of of cluster's average. This dimension was also the only one in which the Slovakia's performance exceeded that recorded for the EU-27, which translated into a narrowing of the digital divide in this area over the analysed period. In relation to the digital leader – Finland, the gap widened in each of the areas analysed, which, as in the case of the Czech Republic and Poland, was due to the much faster pace of change observed in that country.

Hungary, on the other hand, stood out compared to Cluster 2 countries with an above-average annual absolute increment in the general level of digitalization, as well as in Integration of Digital Technology and Digital Public Services dimensions, but the performance in each of the analyzed dimensions was lower than this recorded for the EU-27, resulting in the widening of the digital divide over the analyzed period. The advantage of the Hungarian performance in access over the EU-27 average performance was therefore lost. It is noteworthy, however, that the high pace of change in the Connectivity dimension achieved by Hungary, combined with a lower than the EU27 average annual change recorded in Finland, resulted in a narrowing of the first level digital divide in relation to the DESI ranking leader.

Complementing the results of the cluster analysis for changes in the years 2019-2022, it should be added that cluster 3 grouped the digital leaders of the EU-27, i.e. the countries that ranked in the top 5 of the DESI ranking in 2022. At the same time, the countries of this cluster were, on average, characterized by the highest average annual absolute increment in general digitalization level and in all four dimensions analyzed compared to the other clusters, exceeding (with the exception of the Connectivity area) the EU-27 performance.

The last, fourth cluster includes the Baltic countries - Lithuania, Latvia and Estonia, as well as Luxembourg and Portugal, which, compared to the previous three clusters, had the second highest results in the Human Capital and Digital Public Services dimensions, the second lowest performance in the Integration of Digital Technology and at the same time the lowest results in the Connectivity dimension and DESI value. Only in the first two dimensions mentioned the average pace of change in this cluster exceeded the pace recorded on average in the EU-27.

It can be concluded that in the pandemic period the Visegrad countries showed two distinct patterns of change in digitalization, with the Czech Republic showing similarity to Poland, and Slovakia and Hungary being the second distinct group of countries. Relative to the average EU-27 performance, throughout this period the Czech Republic managed to maintain the pace of change resulting in narrowing of the digital divide in the Digital Public Services dimension. At the same time the change in indices related to DESI, Human Capital and Connectivity area, was insufficient to sustain trends in terms of maintaining an advantage or closing the gap with the EU-27 average. With regard to Poland, the directions of change in the results in individual areas were maintained between 2019 and 2022, which translated into a further narrowing of the gap in relation to the EU27 average performance in the Human Capital

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and Digital Public Services dimensions, while at the same time its widening in two other dimensions and in relation to the overall digitalization score. Similar conclusions can be drawn with regard to the direction of change of the digital divide in Slovakia, where the gap in the Human Capital dimension decreased again in the period 2019-2022 compared to the EU-27 average, while it increased in other dimensions and with regard to the overall digitalization score. In Hungary, the pandemic period resulted in a reversal of the positive changes in the Connectivity dimension and the maintenance of the negative trends in the other dimensions and with regard to the overall digitalization score. This translated into the emergence or further enlargement of the digital divide in each of the analysed dimensions compared to the EU-27 average performance. The pandemic period has therefore brought the narrowing of the divide in skills and digitalization of public services in two out of the four countries analysed compared to the EU-27 results. At the same time, the dimensions where the results deteriorated in each country were the Connectivity and Integration of Digital Technology.

Considering the scale and direction of changes in the values of indices over the entire period covering 2017-2022, it can be concluded that the Czech Republic, Poland and Slovakia managed to catch up with the performance gap in terms of citizens’ digital skills (Human capital dimension), although the scale of these changes varied with Slovakia making the most progress in this respect in relation to the EU-27 average results. Two countries, i.e. the Czech Republic and Poland, managed to catch up in terms of the level of digitalization of public services, with the Czech Republic making significantly more progress in this respect. Hungary, on the other hand, was the only country among the V4 countries analysed where, taking into account the entire period, there was no improvement compared to the EU-27 average results and the digital divide widened in every dimension, including Connectivity dimension, in which in both 2017 and 2019 this country out-performed (Table 13).

Table 13. Selected characteristics on the performance of V4 countries in the period 2017-2022

Country	HC	Conn.	IoDT	DPS	DESI	HC	Conn.	IoDT	DPS	DESI
	Change in the divide between the EU-27 performance and country's performance in 2022 compared to 2017					Change in the divide in 2022 compared to 2017: (-) reduction; (+) increase				
Czechia	-0,1778	1,2168	0,7965	-0,5868	1,2487	(-)	(+)	(+)	(-)	(+)
Hungary	0,5464	0,7962	1,3831	0,3357	3,0613	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)
Poland	-0,1575	2,2939	1,0037	-0,1985	2,9416	(-)	(+)	(+)	(-)	(+)
Slovakia	-0,5758	2,8461	1,3925	1,2346	4,8974	(-)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)
Country	Change in the divide between Finland's performance and country's performance in 2022 compared to 2017					Change in the divide in 2022 compared to 2017: (-) reduction; (+) increase				
	Czechia	0,4524	0,4725	3,4144	0,0971	4,4364	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)
Hungary	1,1765	0,0519	4,0010	1,0196	6,2490	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)
Poland	0,4727	1,5496	3,6216	0,4854	6,1293	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)
Slovakia	0,0543	2,1018	4,0104	1,9185	8,0851	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)	(+)

Source: own elaboration based on DESI data.

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With regard to the EU digital leader Finland, the pandemic period brought a significant increase in this country's performance, resulting in a widening of the asymmetry in Finland's performance compared to the V4 countries, with the exception of the Connectivity dimension, where Hungary managed to catch up. However, taking the entire period 2017-2022 into account, Hungary also recorded a widening digital divide in this area.

5. Discussion

Several recent studies have examined the issue of the digital transformation and the development asymmetries occurring in this respect across the EU, including the V4 countries. Our research builds on the previous research but pays special attention to the performance achieved by all four Visegrad countries: the Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland and Slovakia, analyzing and assessing what results were achieved by V4 countries in the years 2017-2022 in terms of digitalization compared to the other EU countries, what was the scale of the digital divide and how it changed in its different dimensions considering two sub-periods: the pre-pandemic (2017-2019) and the pandemic (2019-2022) period. The clustering of the EU countries according to the average annual absolute increment of the DESI index and its four sub-indices before and during Covid-19 pandemic was helpful to compare and contrast similarities and differences on the pace and structure of digital change between the countries studied.

Our research revealed that the V4 countries in the period analyzed achieved varying levels of digitalization as measured by the DESI index, which is a consequence of the different performance in the four dimensions analyzed. Visegrad countries generally displayed greater mean scores of the four main sub-indices, year by year that also evidenced in EU27 and Finland. The statistics propose an advanced state in the area of Human Capital, Connectivity, Integration of Digital Technology and Digital Public Services. The analysis revealed significant gaps between the Visegrad countries, the EU27 average, and Finland in key areas of digitalization. While the gaps with the EU27 were generally moderate, the disparities with Finland were significant across all dimensions, as Finland sets a high benchmark with its advanced digital infrastructure, skilled workforce, highly digitalized business sector and comprehensive digital public services.

However, while individual V4 countries differ in the rank achieved due to the index value and structure, some overall digital development trends within the V4 countries group are clearly noticeable. Hungary, Poland and Slovakia were among the countries with the lowest digitalization performance in each of the years analyzed, with a slightly better position in this respect observed for the Czech Republic. A comparison of V4 countries indicated therefore for the Czech Republic's stable advantage regarding digitalization. The above findings are largely consistent with those of other authors (Kiseľáková et al., 2021, Pekarcikova et al., 2021, Esses et al., 2021, Čerňanová & Stovíček, 2024). We found that in analyzed years Hungary, Poland and Slovakia were among the digital laggards. Looking at the 2017 and 2022 DESI results, it is

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clear that in both years these three countries have failed to catch up not only with the richer, more developed economies of Western Europe, but also with some of the post-socialist countries of Central and Eastern Europe. They showed slightly better digital performance than Greece, Romania and Bulgaria, which were among the least developed and poorest EU countries. For this reason in the entire period their position compared to other EU countries didn't change, which is due to the weakness of countries lower in the ranking (Hungary, Poland) or deteriorated due to the progress of countries that were able to accelerate their digitalization efforts (Slovakia). Against this background the position of the Czech Republic was more favourable in each of the years analysed that brought this country closer to developed Western European economies, such as Germany, France, Belgium and Austria. However, although the Czech Republic performed better, in 2022 it dropped one position in the DESI ranking (compared to 2017) which was due to Croatia digital progress.

Building on previous studies on digitalization in EU countries, which analysed advances in digitalization in recent years, especially in the pandemic period (Esses et al., 2021, Georgescu et al., 2022) and used different clustering methods to isolate groups of countries with the greatest similarity in terms of the level of digitalization and its advancement in different dimensions (Małkowska et al., 2021, Borowiecki et al., 2021, Kolupaieva & Tiesheva, 2023) we focused on the change that took place in the V4 countries in terms of digitalization in the pre-pandemic and pandemic period. The results of our research are consistent with the findings of other researchers, evidencing that the COVID-19 pandemic acted as a push factor for further development of ICT infrastructure, diffusion of digital technologies and improvement of digital skills. All citizens, organizations regardless of their size or type of activities, were significantly affected by pandemic consequences (Burlea-Schiopoiu et al., 2023). At the same time, health security measures and social distancing policies created an environment forcing a fundamental transformation to a new digital society and economy (Ganichev & Koshovets, 2021, Döhring et al., 2021).

The cluster analysis provided evidence that there were four homogeneous groups of countries showing similarity in the pace and structure of change in the area of digitalization in both sub-periods analyzed. However, there were clear differences in the V4 group in this respect. We found that in both periods the Czech Republic and Poland achieved similar results in terms of the pace and structure of change in the analysed digitalization indices, belonging to the group of countries with a higher average annual absolute increment of analysed indices than Slovakia and Hungary. The latter two countries followed slightly different digital development paths, showing similarity in the pace and structure of digital change only during the pandemic period.

There were different changes observed in the digital divide in particular V4 countries and sub-periods analyzed. In the pre-pandemic period the best results were achieved by the Czech Republic, which managed to narrow the digital divide with respect to the EU27 average score in all dimensions except Integration of Digital Technology. In this period as many as three of the four countries analysed (the Czech Republic, Poland and Slovakia) narrowed the digital

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skills gap, and two out of the four countries improved their performance with respect to EU-27 average in terms of ICT access (the Czech Republic and Hungary) and the digitalization of public services (the Czech Republic and Poland). We can conclude that only some of the V4 countries managed to narrow the digital divide at the analysed two levels and these results are in line with the findings of other scholars. Farkačová et al. (2023) analyzing data from 2015-2020 explained that the Czech Republic and Slovakia achieved higher levels of digital literacy than Hungary due to their strong emphasis on educational reforms and investments in technology infrastructure. The Czech Republic and Slovakia have also prioritized developing digital skills through comprehensive government policies and various initiatives, such as widespread access to educational resources, digital training programs, and technology integration in schools, resulting in a more technologically advanced workforce and higher information literacy rates than Hungary. Also Cseh-Zelina (2023) noticed that although Hungary has launched in this period a number of programs to develop the digital skills of citizens, their results were not reflected in the indicators values. At the same time, he points to the effectiveness of the Hungarian digital infrastructure development measures. They significantly increased the country's performance in this dimension, which helped to narrow the first level divide, what was evidenced in our study. In turn, Piątkowski & Misztal (2022) noting the systematic improvement in the field of public sector's digitalization in Poland stated that this helps to improve the access to and the quality of public services.

With regard to the pandemic period we found that there were significant discrepancies between EU countries in the pace of digitalization, which was also highlighted in the recent literature (Georgescu et al., 2022, Pizar et al., 2024). Although in this period a significant acceleration of the dynamics of digitalization changes in all EU-27 countries was observed, both the cluster analysis and the comparison of the performance of individual V4 countries against the EU-27 average and Finland's results showed that the dynamics of change in the Visegrad countries in many areas was not sufficient to narrow the digital divide. The pandemic period brought a continuation of the positive trend in narrowing of the digital gap in relation to the EU27 average results only in the area of Digital Public Services in the Czech Republic and Poland, as well as in the Human Capital dimension in Poland and Slovakia. At the same time, it brought a break in the positive trend with regard to the Human Capital dimension in the Czech Republic and Connectivity in the Czech Republic and Hungary. In other cases, the negative trends were maintained, resulting in a further widening of the gap.

Considering the entire period covering 2017-2022 the narrowing of the digital skills divide in the Czech Republic, Poland and Slovakia should be regarded as a particularly positive trend. According to Maziarz (2023) it constitutes the critical condition for the proper development of the information society, which by its nature should be oriented towards innovations, dynamic technological progress and competitiveness. Without an adequate level of advanced digital skills, this is impossible to achieve. Also research by Laitso et al. (2020) emphasizes the role of digital skill enhancement, alongside broadband penetration, in driving

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economic growth and reducing inequality within the EU. The study suggests that targeted investments in these areas can help bridge the digital divide.

The reduction of the usage divide in public services in the Czech Republic and Poland should also be assessed positively, as it improves the quality of citizens' life and doing business, also intensifying the use of ICT by them (Fischer et al., 2021). A disturbing phenomenon was noted in relation to Hungary performance, where, taking into account the entire period, it was not possible to narrow the divide in any of the dimensions studied. However, worth noting is that despite the divide Hungary was exceptionally advanced in Connectivity among the V4 countries. In the period analysed, the V4 countries also failed to reduce the gap between them and digital leader – Finland.

Our research evidenced, similarly as those of the other authors, that Internet penetration and physical access to the Internet was growing in recent years across the whole Europe, but particularly in technologically advanced countries (Ragnedda & Kreitem, 2018). For this reason the differences in terms of access still persist and the Visegrad countries failed to keep up the pace of improvement in this field comparing to the average results in the EU-27. The efforts in boosting the Internet infrastructures and all the associated policies adopted were not sufficient to close the first level digital divide in these countries. Digitalization efforts in the V4 countries also failed when it comes to the second level divide related to digitalization of the business sector, especially SMEs, what was also evidenced by studies of Hunady et al. (2022) and Kovács et al. (2023). V4 countries performance in the area of digitalization of business remained well below the EU-27 average with important progress still needed in terms of the uptake of advanced technologies. However, the under-performance in this field can be partly explained by the specific structure of their economy. Although the Visegrad countries are strongly integrated with global value chains, they are recognized as highly dependent on foreign capital (FDI). Leaving aside the foreign-owned automotive and electronic industry, the Visegrád countries are less prepared for the digital transition than many of their Western European peers (Szabo, 2020). In particular, small and medium-sized enterprises, which make up a large part of their economy, have a low uptake of digital technologies (Chetverikova, 2023). Local firms lag behind foreign companies in terms of digitalization for many reasons, including the low level of innovation and a lack of financing (Rosak-Szyrocka et al., 2021, Krajčík, 2021, Olšanová, et al., 2021). The persistent duality between domestic and foreign firms means that the dependence of the Visegrad digitalization model will be further strengthened, especially in relation to all Industry 4.0 technologies, which will not be conducive to the rapid digitalization of the business sector in these countries (Éltető et al., 2022). It also leads to the conclusions important from the point of view of policies aiming at narrowing the use divide in business sector that the technology adoption is a much wider issue than the issue of access or skills (Kurakova et al., 2021). The critical condition is also to ensure the positive external effects and spillovers from more advanced foreign firms to local companies. It should be noted, however, that poor business digitalization is a problem not only for the Visegrad countries. Some studies evidenced that countries classified as digital access leaders, having

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advanced digital infrastructure and high levels of digital access, record also an imbalance or underperformance in the uptake of digital technologies in the business sector (Pinto *et al.*, 2023; OECD, 2021). They point to a potential gap between digital infrastructure and the degree of absorption and integration of digital technologies in enterprises, resulting from lack of the necessary infrastructure or resources to implement them effectively.

Despite significant efforts made in recent years to bridge the digital divide at its different levels in Visegrad countries, our research results clearly show, they are not very effective and do not bring such tangible results as in many other EU countries, which results in a widening of the digital divide in most of the dimensions analyzed. These gaps highlight the need for targeted investments in digital infrastructure, education, and public services. Enhancing digital skills and connectivity can enable the V4 countries to better leverage digital technologies, improve public service delivery, and foster economic growth. Addressing these challenges will require comprehensive digital strategies, public-private partnerships, and a focus on inclusive digital transformation.

6. Conclusions

As stated in the introduction, the primary purpose of this study was to to analyse and assess the digital divide between the Visegrad countries and the EU-27 countries in the years 2017-2022. We have shown how strongly digital divide in terms of digital access, digital skills and use is evident between these countries and the other EU Members. In this way we have illustrated the strengths and weaknesses of the digital development in individual V4 countries. We have also uncovered major similarities and contrasts in the digital divide among these countries in two specific sub-periods covering the pre-pandemic and pandemic years. The study results suggest the existence of rather significant differences in the level of digital development among the V4 countries with varying achievements in four dimensions of digitalization compared to the EU-27 average and EU digital leader results. Our research therefore brings the conclusion that it is inappropriate to view the Visegrad Group as a coherent block of countries, as there are still digital inequalities corresponding to different levels of the digital divide, related to the access, as well as digital skills and use of ICT, reflecting different levels of advancement of the digital transformation in these countries. We have also noticed, that Czech Republic constantly scores better than the other three countries, showing higher performance in terms of ICT access, digital skills and digital use in business sector and public services. It can therefore be assumed that this country can be a kind of benchmark for the digitalization efforts of other V4 countries. Our findings accentuate also the importance of targeted policy interventions to bridge gaps within Visegrad countries to be more closely aligned with EU benchmarks. Policymakers can benefit from these insights to identify areas needing improvement as per benchmarking analysis to highlight and plan for digital

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infrastructure, policy development and framework, and targeted investment relating to digitalization.

In terms of whether the digital divide in Visegrad countries was narrowing or widening compared to average EU results, we argue that both processes took, in fact, place, in relation to the different levels of the divide. However, even in dimensions where positive changes have occurred, there is still considerable room for improvement. Moreover, bridging the digital divide in digital skills and the digitalization of public services has not yet been matched by improvements in the business sector, confirming a much broader set of factors critical to the use of ICT in business. Our findings therefore underline the need to rethink national strategies for the digitalization of the business sector, as those currently implemented do not seem to be delivering the expected results. However, it can be also expected, that the use of ICT in these countries will accelerate soon, as the better digitally educated individuals will be more likely to use them.

Despite of our effort to present a complete and multidimensional analysis, some limitations must be recognized. First, our empirical analysis relates the digital divide among V4 countries compared to the EU, which means that all indices used were considered at an aggregate level related to the national level. For this reason, we could not analyze the digital divide at the internal, domestic level. Moreover, our analysis does not allow us to identify specific reasons for the difference in the state of the digital divide in V4 countries. The identified directions of change in the digital divide in the V4 countries, and especially the widening of the gap resulting from the insufficient dynamics of digital changes, require an in-depth analysis of the reasons for the poor progress of these countries. This determines the directions of future research. At the same time, the better performance of the Czech Republic compared to the other three countries should encourage to discover the underlying reasons for this situation in search of improvement potential in three other countries. Finally, due to the set of indicators included in the DESI we have studied only two out of three levels of digital divide without taking into account the third level divide. However the results of this study form the basis for an empirical study of these issues in our further research to recognize concrete offline outcomes resulting from differentiated access, digital literacy and the use of ICT.

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